

Linguistics studies in social-interactional perspectives

In its third edition of 2022, *Revista Letras Raras (RLR)* presents a robust issue entitled **Linguistic studies from social-interactional perspectives**. Organised and edited by the research group LELLC (Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity, Federal University of Campina Grande), we have the immeasurable contribution of professors/scholars from four different institutions: Federal University of Pernambuco (Brazil); Federal University of Campina Grande (Brazil); and Boston College (United States of America). Thereby, the organisers of this issue: Ricardo Rios Barreto Filho, Herbertt Neves, Otávia Pinheiro Pedrosa Fernandes, and Mariana Lima Becker selected the texts by the researchers who attended the call for papers. Following a careful evaluation that includes other colleagues from several other higher education and federal institutions, this issue reaches the public with nineteen papers that go through Discourse Analysis, as well as through the study of language in a social-interactional perspective.

Furthermore, the public will be able to read a review that gives an idea concerning the research on the practice of linguistic analysis in Elementary Education, as a field of work of the Literature professional; that is, through the social-interactional paths yet. The reading of two interviews is also a passageway to better understand the theme proposed in this issue, given that it is so present in the daily life of professionals of languages.

The nineteen papers published here have their researchers from different institutions, namely: Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Boston College (BC), Federal University of Viçosa (UFV), Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP), Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Agreste of Pernambuco (UFAPE), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), State University of Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), State University of Rio Grande do Norte (UERN), Federal Institute of Pernambuco (IFSPE), St. James International School, State University of Londrina (UEL), and Pontifical Catholic University of Minas Gerais (PUC-Minas).

The diversity of texts is also foundational for investigations on Linguistics, with an emphasis on the perspective of social-interactional studies as an important milestone of this journal, which launches an issue totally focused on the theme. Once more, the esteemed reader will be faced with an edition

that seeks to share research and main reflections for our mastery of languages, in this **Linguistic studies from social-interactional perspectives**.

Once again, reading and sharing the papers in this issue becomes a *sine qua non* of survival and resistance against all the onslaughts of denial of science, against research in the areas of the Humanities and, especially, in search of a human Brazil.

Let us, therefore, share knowledge; there is no other meaning for it, except when it is shared!

Dear reader, let us resist and survive!

In the certainty of this sharing, we wish you a great reading!

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PhD Prof. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva (UEPB, Brazil)
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Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral